

Review on Biodiesel Production from Sandbox (Hura Crepitans) Seed Oil Used In Compression Ignition (C.I.) Engine

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 02 Sep 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Biodiesel Sandbox Hura Crepitans Compression Ignition Diesel, Engine, Performance, Emission.</p>	<p>The rising concern over the exhaust emissions yielded by the increased demand for diesel as well as the realization that diesel is non-renewable has triggered various initiatives to search for more environmentally friendly and sustainable alternatives. The goal of this study is to review the processes involved in the extraction of biodiesel from sandbox (Hura Crepitans) seed oils and analyze the performance of the engine operating under diesel engine thermodynamic conditions. This review describes the sandbox oil and biodiesel yield and sandbox oil performance with biodiesel blends in operating diesel engines. Literature provided data contrasting conventional diesel with diesel-biodiesel blends that showed the diesel-biodiesel blend had lower ignition delay coupled with a lower heat release rate and slightly better efficiency.</p>

1. Introduction

Depleting petroleum reserves on the earth and increasing concerns about the environment leads to the quest for fuels which are eco-friendly and safe for human beings. Among various options investigated for alternative fuels, Biodiesel obtained from vegetable oils has been recognized world over as one of the strong contenders for reductions in exhaust emissions and is favorably viewed as a potential green alternative fuel. Moreover, despite the technical feasibility, vegetable oils as fuel could not get acceptance, as they were more expensive than petroleum fuels. These become a challenge to scientists and engineers to identify appropriate feed stocks for biodiesel. Though, there is much research in biodiesel production from oils seeds worldwide. Typical raw materials of biodiesel are rapeseed oil, canola oil, soybean oil, sunflower oil and palm sheep tallow and poultry oil from animal sources and cooking oil are also sources of raw materials, (Printo *et al.*, 2005).

Alternative fuel and energy sources like coal, natural gas, ethanol, methane, hydrogen, geothermal, nuclear, solar, hydro and wind all have problems associated with scaling them up to replace cheap oil. Even if you add up all these alternatives, they will not even come close to the equivalent of 28 billion barrel of oil a year (James *et al.*, 2003). Out of all these, biodiesel has the most potential end promise, yet it is a drop in the bucket compared to fossil fuels.

1.1 Definition of biodiesel

- ✓ Biodiesel is the name for a variety of ester-based fuels (fatty esters) generally defined as the monoalkyl esters made from vegetable oils, such as soybean oil, canola or hemp oil, or sometimes from animal fats through a simple transesterification process. (Cyberlipid)
- ✓ Biodiesel is an alternative fuel for diesel engine, where it is produced by chemically reacting a vegetable oil or animal fat with alcohol such as methanol and ethanol. (Hanh, *et al.*, 2007)
- ✓ Biodiesel IS defined as mono-alkyl ester of long chain fatty acids derived from vegetable oils or animal fats which conform to ASTM D6751(American society of testing and materials standard) specifications for use in diesel engines. It refers to the pure fuel blending with diesel fuel. Biodiesel blends are denoted as "BXX" with

"XX" representing the percentage of biodiesel contained in the blend (B20 is 20%biodiesel,80% petroleum diesel), (Mark *et al.*,2003) feedstock that can be used in diesel engines as neat fuel.

- ✓ Biodiesel is a fuel obtained from renewable biomass blended at various proportions with convectional fossil diesel fuel (Van,2005)

1.2 Feedstock used in production biodiesel.

Biodiesel can be synthesized from various raw materials, including vegetable oils, animal fats, algae, and waste cooking oil. Each feedstock has its own advantages and challenges regarding availability, cost, sustainability, and energy content. The purpose of using different raw materials is to diversify the sources of renewable energy and reduce dependence on fossil fuels. At least 80% of the current costs of producing biodiesel come from the feedstock (Sayed and El Gharbawy, 2016). Given the global food crisis, almost 95% of biodiesel produced worldwide is manufactured from edible oils, which are viewed as unnecessary (Azizian and Kramer 2005). As a result, making biodiesel from inexpensive, non-edible oil is the current trend (Balat 2011). A few feedstocks, including palm, jatropha, microalgae, coconut tallow, and used cooking oil, stand out for their high productivity in the manufacturing of biodiesel (Gui *et al.*, 2008). The choice of raw materials has a significant impact on the production of biodiesel in terms of yield, quality, cost, and environmental sustainability. The fatty acid profile of the raw material plays a crucial role in determining the properties and performance of biodiesel. Oils with high levels of saturated fatty acids produce biodiesel with better cold flow properties, while oils with high levels of unsaturated fatty acids produce biodiesel with better oxidative stability (Suzihaque *et al.*, 2022). FFA content significantly impacts the reaction rate and biodiesel yield. Higher FFA content requires pre-treatment steps, such as esterification, to reduce acidity and prevent soap formation, which can hinder the reaction and reduce biodiesel purity (Javidialesaadi and Raeissi, 2013). The amount of water in the raw material can also affect the transesterification reaction. Excess water can hydrolyze the fatty acid methyl esters produced during the reaction, reducing biodiesel yield. Therefore, feedstocks with low water content are preferred (Atadashi *et al.*, 2012).

1.3 *Sandbox (hura crepitans) seeds as feedstock*

Hura crepitans (sandbox) tree is a tropical plant belonging to the family Euphorbiaceae. In Nigeria, this plant is known as "odan Mecca" by the Kabba people of Kogi State and "aroyin" by the Ijesha people of Osun State. Hura crepitans is a widely occurring self-regenerating ornamental plant in the tropics and frequently planted in towns and villages as cover tree. It has a short, densely crowned spines on the trunk and branches, and the long-stalked leaves with notably closely parallel pinnate nerves. This tree flowers usually at the beginning and at the end of rainy season. Hura crepitans can be used as purgative. Its oil-bearing seed is under-utilized, marginalized or neglected despite its high oil content (over 50%). It is non-edible, available at little or no cost of purchase and can be planted on marginal lands (Giwa, et al. 2016)

2. Oil extraction from Sandbox seed

Several sources of oil (edible, non-edible, waste, microalgae) and fats have been employed for biodiesel production, though edible oils are the most abundant and most utilized. Some of the edible oils are from soybean, palm, rapeseed, sunflower, peanut, mustard, lin, tallow fat, seeds etc., (Asokan et al. 2019 and Mahmudul et al. 2017) and the non-edible oils are from jojoba, jatropha, Karanja, cotton, castor, seeds etc. (Babazadeh, 2017, Rajak et al, 2018 and Singh et al. 2018). The sustainability of the fuel will not be feasible because relying on edible oil sources could lead to food scarcity and a hike in food prices (Naylor et al, 2018). Effectively harnessing non-edible oil sources owing to the availability of relevant biomass sources and arable lands for cultivation is an important point of consideration in biodiesel production (Subramanian, 2018). Sandbox (Hura crepitans) also known as possum wood is an evergreen tree of the spurge family (Euphorbiaceae). Sandbox tree is a widely grown tree in towns and villages all around the tropical vegetation of the earth as a shade tree owing to its wide-spreading branches. It has small and pointed spines that are densely crowded around the trunk and branches.

The woody fruits resemble small pumpkin pods, a hard-protective coat in which the seeds are housed/enclosed with about 13–16 seeds in a radial and circular arrangement around the central axis of the pod. Some authors have worked on the extraction and characterization of the oil and reported

oil yields of 37.78 and 36.40% respectively (Ezeh et al. 2012 and Oderinde et al. 2009) suggesting that the seed has a good potential for oil production. In other studies, an improved oil yield of 51.43% (Fowomola et al. 2007), 47.80% (Oyekunle et al. 2008), 52.73% (Amoo et al. 2012), 69.32% (Eloka-Eboka et al. 2017) and 72.20% (Ibrahim et al. 2019). All these outcomes show that Sandbox oil is a sustainable feedstock for biodiesel production.

3. Biodiesel Production

A successful alternative fuel is one that guarantees environmental friendliness from lowered exhaust emissions and also ensures efficiency of operation (Shailaja et al., 2013). Biodiesels are considered to be more suitable than conventional diesel because of their bio-component which makes them biodegradable, nontoxic, clean and renewable. The use of biodiesel reduces environmentally degrading emissions such as CO, sulfur compounds and unburned hydrocarbons when compared to diesel. According to (Demirbas, 2012), biodiesel refers to diesel fuels from biological materials. It is a range of long chain fatty acid esters produced from various edible and non-edible lipids such as vegetable oils, waste or used cooking oils, automobile oils or animal fat (Gui et al., 2008). A product of the transesterification reaction between lipids of organic origin and alcohol of low molecular mass in a hydroxide (mainly sodium or potassium) aided catalyst reaction; biodiesel therefore is a renewable biofuel (Haas et al., 2004).

The source of Biodiesel usually depends on the crops amenable to the regional climate. In the United States, soybean oil is the most commonly Biodiesel feedstock, whereas the rapeseed (canola) oil and palm oil are the most common source for Biodiesel, in Europe, and in tropical countries respectively (Singh et al., 2010). A suitable source to produce Biodiesel should not compete with other applications that rise prices, for example pharmaceutical raw materials. But the demand for pharmaceutical raw material is lower than for fuel sources. As much as possible the Biodiesel source should fulfill two requirements: low production costs and large production scale. Refined oils have high production costs, but low production scale; on the other side, waste cooking oil (WCO), non-edible seeds, algae and sewerage have low production costs and are more available than refined or recycled oils (Mulla et al., 2017).

Fig. 1: Biodiesel cycle

3.1 Importance of biodiesel as a renewable energy source.

Biodiesel has many environmental beneficial properties. The main importance of biodiesel is that it can be described as 'carbon neutral'. This means that the biodiesel produces it has no output of carbon in the form of carbon dioxide (CO₂). This effect occurs because when the oil crop grows it absorbs the same amount of CO₂ as is released when the fuel is combusted. This is not completely accurate as CO₂ is released during the production of the fertilizer required to fertilize the fields in which the oil crops are grown. Assessment of the impact of all these sources requires the use of a technique called life cycle analysis. Tri-state biodiesel (TSB) reported that the importance of biodiesel is;

i. Biodiesel reduces harmful emissions that cause environmental problems such as global warming, acid rain, and smog. Biodiesel reduces CO₂ emissions by over 78% compared to petroleum diesel (U.S Department of Energy, 2020).

- ii. Health problems as a result of emission exposure are also greatly reduced by the cleaner emissions of biodiesel. According to the American Lung Association biodiesel emissions are 90% less toxic than petro-diesel and will reduce incidents of health hazards such as asthma, emphysema, and lung cancer.
- iii. Biodiesel is domestically produced. Biodiesel benefits American farmers, American businesses, and the national economy. Job creation, new markets for domestic agricultural products, and keeping our energy dollars domestic are just a few of the many economic benefits gained by using biodiesel instead of petroleum diesel.
- iv. Biodiesel is a renewable fuel source. Unlike fossil fuels, biodiesel is made from vegetable oil seed crops which replenish the market annually with renewable feedstock.
- v. Biodiesel is biodegradable and non-toxic. Biodiesel handling and use is far less damaging to the environment than petroleum fuel.

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- vi. Biodiesel can be used alone or mixed in any proportion with petroleum diesel fuel. A 20% blend of biodiesel with diesel fuel is called "B20," a 5% blend is called "B5" and so on.
- vii. Biodiesel has superior lubrication quality than that of diesel fuel. It increases engine life and can be used to replace sulfur, the acid-rain-causing lubricating agent in petroleum diesel.
- viii. Biodiesel is safer to transport. Biodiesel has a high flash point, or ignition temperature, of about 300°F compared to petroleum diesel fuel, which has a flash point of 125°F.
- ix. Engines running on biodiesel run normally and have similar fuel mileage to engines running on diesel fuel. Auto ignition, fuel consumption, power output, and engine torque are relatively unaffected by biodiesel.

3.2 Transesterification

Among the various methods, Biodiesel is commonly produced by the transesterification of vegetable oil or animal fat feedstock because it is the most economical process requiring only low temperatures and pressures are required in the production. Transesterification (also called alcoholysis) is the chemical reaction of a fat or oil with an alcohol to form esters and glycerol. A catalyst is usually used to improve the reaction rate and yield.

Fig. 2: chemical process for methyl ester
Where R's are long-chain hydrocarbons

The transesterification reaction is stirred and often heated to accelerate the reaction. The residence time within a batch transesterification reaction varies from 1-8 hours, depending on the composition of their agent and reactors conditions (MDAC, 2003).

It is important to note that free fatty acids present within the triglycerides must be monitored to ensure that soap is not formed. After reacting, two phases are formed, the glycerol and alcohol phase, and the biodiesel phase because glycerol has a higher specific gravity and is immiscible in the biodiesel phase. Once the glycerol phase is separated, the alcohol is then removed from the biodiesel by distillation or flash evaporation. The final biodiesel product must comply with ASTM D6751 to be within specification (NBB 2003).

Biodiesel has been produced from sandbox seeds with acceptable properties mostly through a two-step transesterification reaction. For example, Adepoju produced biodiesel from sandbox seed with a yield of 92.7% (Adepoju et al. 2013). Adewuyi et al. had a biodiesel yield of 98.7% (Adewuyi et al. 2014), Otokhian et al. had a biodiesel yield of 82% (Otokhian et al. 2016). Eloka-Eboka et al. reported 98.53% yield (Eloka-Eboka et al. 2017). Oyelade et al. produces biodiesel with 93% yield (Oyelade et al. 2017). Akintunde et al. also obtained 86.49% yield (Akintunde et al. 2021). All these previous studies employed a two-step transesterification reaction, which involved pre-treatment of the oil in the first step followed by transesterification in the second stage.

4. Performance and emission characteristics in ci engine

Compared to petro diesel fuel, burning biodiesel releases fewer particulates, carbon monoxide, and unburned hydrocarbons. Since biodiesel is produced using natural resources, its sulfur content is relatively low, which means that when it burns in an engine, it releases less sulfur dioxide into the atmosphere (Rayati et al. 2020). All biodiesels and their blends have shown the capacity to enhance gas turbine performance while

lowering emissions of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxide, and hydrocarbons under a range of operating conditions. To employ fuels

in an engine, one must be aware of their characteristics for combustion. Although fossil fuel-based diesel fuel may not be entirely replaced by biodiesel, it can aid in achieving balanced energy utilization. One benefit is that biodiesel may be used in contemporary engines with little modification. Older vehicles with natural rubber gasoline lines, however, require a few modifications. Rubber fuel lines must be replaced since they will crack when used with biodiesel. On the other hand, an oil or gasoline dilution in the fuel system is possible in a modern vehicle with a DPF (diesel particulate filter). The ability of gasoline to lubricate the fuel injection system is believed to be crucial for diesel engines. The use of diesel-biodiesel mixes can thereby enhance their general lubricity. Additionally, the lower sulfur level of today's diesel fuel could affect its lubricity because the compounds that provided lubrication are no longer present (Veza et al. 2022).

The ASTM and the European biodiesel standards have globally standardized these characteristics. Some of these properties are acid value, kinematic viscosity, density, flash point, pour point, cetane number, iodine value, etc. Biodiesel can be blended with petro diesel and sometimes with other additives to improve its properties for engine combustion (Hosamani and Katti, 2018; Jayaprabakar et al., 2019). Combustion of biodiesel has been done in different types of diesel engines both experimentally and numerically at varying conditions to evaluate the sustainability of the biofuel (Suresh et al., 2018). EL-Seesy, et al. enhanced jojoba biodiesel/diesel blends with 10% n-butanol as an oxygenated additive in the test fuels. A drastic reduction in the GHG emitted was observed, up to 80%, 80% and 65% reduction in NO_x, CO and UHC respectively were reported with a slight decrease in the heat release rate (EL-Seesy et al., 2019). Sandouqa and Al-Hamamre also evaluated the energy efficiency of jojoba oil biodiesel. This involved other by-products such as fertilizer, glycerine,

husk residue etc., and concluded that a net energy balance of 46724.1 MJ/ha was obtainable. Also, an estimate of 66.0 g CO₂ eq/MJ biodiesel of GHG was produced and a reduction of 9.52% in energy input was estimated possible by reusing the joboba manure (Sandouqa and Al-Hamamre, 2019). Shote, et al. tested 9 blends (in ratio 1:9–9:1) of palm kernel oil (PKO) biodiesel–diesel and compared them with pure PKO biodiesel and pure diesel to evaluate the emissions. It was found that an increase in the percentage of biodiesel reduces CO emission by 35% and that emissions of NO_x do not depend directly on biodiesel except if there is a rise in the effluent temperature (Shote et al., 2019). Uyumaz combusted three blends (M10, M20, and M30) of mustard oil biodiesel at different engine loads and compared them with petrodiesel (D100). The study concluded that there was no significant cylinder pressure change for fuels. Also, reduction in BTE by 6.8%, in smoke by 32.9%, in CO by 50.4% but increase in BSFC by 4.8%, in NO_x by 22.1% was obtained in the blends (Uyumaz, 2018). Musthafa, et al. compared three test fuels, diesel, B20 (20% palm oil biodiesel blend) and BD1 (B20 + 1% di-tert-butyl peroxide (DTBP)). DTBP was added as a cetane number improver. CO and NO_x reduction by 13%–15% was observed as well in BSEC by 10%–15%. Also, a little increase in UHC, and BTE by 2–3.5% was observed (Musthafa et al., 2018). Di Blasio et al. have also blended other biofuels with diesel such as glycerol-based ethers (GEM) (Di Blasio et al., 2013) and methane (Di Blasio et al., 2017), in which glycerol is a by-product of the transesterification process of biodiesel production. They examined the sustainability of diesel/GEM blends in a diesel engine and found an appreciable drop in all the emissions including NO_x (Di Blasio et al., 2013).

5. Conclusion

This review highlights sandbox seed oil's promise as a non-food feedstock for biodiesel, reducing competition with food resources. The oil yield from sandbox seed oil as a non-edible feedstock is quite significant, with reported oil yield ranging from 47 percent to 72 percent based on extraction methods. Furthermore, biodiesel yield using optimized transesterification techniques meets global fuel production standards with consistent yields over 85 percent and some studies even reporting up to 98 percent.

Engine performance evaluations indicate that sandbox seed oil biodiesel can successfully fuel compression ignition engines when blended with conventional diesel. While there is some observed reduction in brake power and increase in fuel consumption as compared to fossil diesel, marked decreases in exhaust emissions of carbon monoxide, unburned hydrocarbons, particulate matter, and carbon dioxide have been documented. 60% reduction in CO and HC emissions as well as significant particulate emission reduction have been observed. The reduction in emissions from biodiesel makes it a far more effective fuel. as compared to conventional diesel. The reduction in emissions from biodiesel makes it a far more effective fuel. However, still needing to be addressed is the problem of higher emissions of NO_x.

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